

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG EMPLOYEES IN AAVIN CO - OPERATIVE IN SALEM

Ms.B.Vasuki, Assistant professor of Business Administration and Head of the department, Theivanai Ammal college for women Autonomous Villupuram, Tamilnadu India.

Sneha.E , Mohana.A, Kaviya.R, Hemamalini.M Students of business Administration, Theivanai Ammal college for women Autonomous Villupuram, Tamilnadu India.

ABSTRACT

Employee commitment, which includes no excessive workload, is a factor that influences motivation, retention, and goal achievement at work treating employee with respect, providing recognition & rewards, fringe benefits and positive management. The purpose of this topic is to study the employee satisfaction and organization commitment, as well as to investigate staff satisfaction levels and how they affect commitment. Purposive sampling is employed in this descriptive and empirical study. The study is based on first-hand information that has been gathered. 50 respondents have been chosen at random from a structural questionnaire completed by member states, and the percentage technique is utilized to analyse the results. The results of this study show that employee satisfaction affects management and staff commitment. Rewards, stress, leave, perks, and salary provided to the employees by management are factors affecting employee commitment and motivation. These factors are crucial to raising motivation levels and enhancing employee satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: working conditions, development opportunities, work output, nature of work itself.

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this study is to determine whether employees are happy with their specific job descriptions and titles, whether they can manage work stress, whether they can find motivation, and whether they can adjust to various leadership philosophies. Does the boss assist the employee in finding a work-life balance when it comes to the question of whether or not the employee can handle the workload? Employee satisfaction is defined as the level of contentment and gratification that an employee feels toward his or her overall employment, taking into account how satisfied the employee is with the job itself, the coworkers, the managers, and the company policies. There are numerous challenges that affect an employee's happiness with his or her work and with the organization, regardless of where they are in the organizational structure. He and the company might not be happy with the direction he is taking.

- To determine the employee's degree of satisfaction.
- To assess the strength of the link between organizational commitment and employee happiness.
- To pinpoint key determinants of employee commitment to the company and satisfaction with their work.

Job happiness is the sense of fulfillment one experiences while working, which serves as a driving force to continue working. It is the pleasure at work rather than self-satisfaction, happiness, or contentment. When an impulse achieves its goal, satisfaction refers to the straightforward emotional state that goes along with it. The variables influencing both job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction were described differently by research participants. "Job satisfaction" is defined as a pleasant or positive emotional state brought on by one's employment or professional experience. "The level of pleasure or contentment connected to a work is known as job satisfaction.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jawa (1971) collected data on 70 semi-skilled workers in his study on anxiety and job satisfaction. On the basis of the anxiety scale filled by the respondents and their scores, anxiety was divided into three groups of high, average and low anxiety. In addition to this, a satisfaction

questionnaire was also filled by the respondents. The results indicate a trend of increasing satisfaction with decreasing anxiety level.

Smith, Scott and Hulin (1977) selected 4000 managers of the 145 company for the sample of the study on Job satisfaction of professional employees of the company. It was found out through this research that satisfaction increase with the age. Thus, indicating a positive relation of Job satisfaction with the age.

Richmond, McCroskey and Davis (1982), stated that "moderately satisfied employees may be more productive than dissatisfied employee; extremely satisfied employees may form the type of work group known as the "happiness for lunch bunch" (**McCroskey, Larson & Knapp 1971**)-and be more of a social group than a work group, hence lowering productivity.

Bhatt (1987) studied the personality determinations of Job satisfaction of college teachers of Saurashtra University and all college teachers were included in the sample of the study. It was found that female teachers were more satisfied than male teachers, also no significant difference was found in the mean scores of married and unmarried teachers. It was also found that Job satisfaction had no significant relation with the age, area of the work, educational qualification and experience.

Sharma (1987) examined the effects of work culture on employee satisfaction, sense of participation, role stress and alienation in private sector and public sector and found that the private sector and the public sector varied significantly on the dominant culture variables and there was significant correlation between the work culture variable and role stress variables.

Rajendran (1987) in a public sector industry highlighted a significant correlation between work culture and employee satisfaction.

Rain et al., (1991) stated that job satisfaction has a correlation with life satisfaction. People who are satisfied with life will tend to be satisfied with the job and vice versa.

Cardona (1996) in a survey of members of the Association for Investment Management and Research found that 81% of the managers were satisfied or very satisfied with their job. Most managers named professional achievement, personal or professional growth, the work itself and their degree of responsibility more important than compensation as the factors that create

positive feelings about their job. Factors like company policies, administration, relationships with supervisors, compensation and the negative impact of work on their personal lives were viewed as those which create negative feelings about the job.

National Center for Education Statistics, (1997) in a report on job satisfaction among American teachers identified that more administrative support and leadership, good student such as age and gender have little or no significant impact on job satisfaction.

Karl & Sutton (1998) found that from an employee point of view, job satisfaction is a desirable outcome in itself. While from a managerial or organizational effectiveness point, job satisfaction is important due to its impact on absenteeism (1) turnover, (2) and pro-social "citizenship" behaviors such as helping co-workers, helping customers, and being more cooperative. Thus it becomes important for the managers to understand what employees value in order to redesign jobs, reward systems, and human resource management policies that will result in optimum job satisfaction and productivity.

Gohil (1999) studied on the motivation vis-à-vis job satisfaction and organizational perception of bank employees in Saurashtra region and was confined to the officer and clerical staff of the public sector commercial banks of the Saurashtra region. The study was conducted on 780 employees and a significant difference was found in the average scores of job satisfaction of managerial cadre and clerical. A significant difference was also observed between (a) academic qualification and means scores of job satisfaction. (b) family tension and means scores of job satisfaction, (c) family environment and means scores of job satisfaction. The study also highlighted the correlation in length of service and means scores of job satisfaction.

Ali and Akhtar (1999) studied and explored the effect which work culture has on employees' satisfaction and found that those who scored high on work culture also differed significantly on satisfaction scale.

Wiggins & Bowman (2000) studied the relationship among career experience, life satisfaction, and organizational factors for managers. The study was conducted in health care organizations. Nine domains of important job skills, knowledge, and abilities necessary for success as health care managers were identified in a two stage Delphi analysis of American College of Healthcare Executives (ACHE) members. Cost/finance, leadership, professional staff

interactions,healthcaredeliveryconcepts,accessibility,ethics,quality/riskmanagement,technology, and marketing weretheninedomains.

Castro and Martin (2010),stated that the studyis to explore the relationship betweenorganizational climate and Job Satisfaction and to determine whether employee's perceptions ofwork environment influenced their level of Job Satisfaction. Questionnairewas administered tothe sample of 696 employees from a population of 1453 employeesworking in three regions inwhich the organization was operational. Confirmatory andexplanatory factor analyses were usedto investigate the structure of the climate model. Thefindings of the study indicated a positiverelationshipbetweenorganization climatescoresand Job satisfactionscores.

Gurusamy&Mahendran (2013), in their study found that Salary occupy the First Rankfordeterminingjobsatisfactioncomparedwithothermajordeterminants.Thestudywasconducted on 300 respondents andwas limited to theautomobileindustries ofIndia.

Rashid Saced et al., (2014), in his study found promotion, pay, fairness and workingcondition to be the key factors that contribute to employee job satisfaction. The study wasconducted on 200 telecom sector employees of Pakistan. It was concluded that money andcompensationplay an importantrolein thejob satisfaction ofthetelecomemployeesofPakistan.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It is claimed that a happy employee is a productive employee, and that any type ofcomplaintoveranorganizationorapersonalmatterwillhaveagreaterimpactontheworkplace.As a result, every firm places a larger focus on maintaining employee happiness byoffering a number of amenities that raise contentment and lower dissatisfaction.The entrepreneurviews job satisfaction as a critical issue where efforts are made and programmers are started.Employee dissatisfaction can lead to absenteeism, poor turnover, and lower productivity. Makingerrors and directing energy towards various conflicts With this in mind, all businesses work toidentify the areas where satisfaction can be raised in order to avoid the pitfallsmentionedabove.In this regard, AAVIN conducted a poll to ascertain employee satisfaction levels in termsofhowstronglythey agreeorstrongly disagreewithcertain aspects oftheir jobs.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research can be viewed as a planned activity with clear goals and objectives on a topic or issue, supported by the collection of relevant analytical tools and the drawing of sound conclusions based on the data. It is a planned investigation. A method of systematically addressing the research challenge is known as research methodology. In research methodology, we look at the many approaches typically used by a researcher to investigate his research problem and the reasoning behind them. Also, research must comprehend the presumptions that underlie the various methodologies and be aware of the differences between some issues and others. Employees with an average satisfaction metrics score of nine or higher are included in this category. Employees that are happy with their jobs are also happy with their pay. A corporation will display high engagement levels if the workplace is productive is a sign of a person's level of satisfaction with their employment. Working circumstances, pay, comfort and safety at work, as well as the nature of their work, are typical aspects influencing complicated satisfaction.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Primary objectives:

- To determine the level of workplace satisfaction at Aavin Cooperative.

Secondary objectives:

- To ascertain the level of employee satisfaction
- To assess the strength of the link between corporate commitment and employee satisfaction.
- To pinpoint key determinants of employee commitment to the organisation and happiness with their work.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between the employee job satisfaction with respect to their Demographic Variable.

V. RESULT&DISCUSSION

TableNo.1DemographicCharacteristicsofonlineConsumers.

S. No	Particulars	No.OfRespondents	Percentage
	AgeGroup		
1	Lessthan25	11	21
2	26to 35	19	36
3	36to 45	16	30
4	46above	7	13
	EducationQualification		
5	School	12	23
6	Graduate	30	57
7	Postgraduate	5	9
8	Profession	6	11

The table 1 explains the demographic factors of the employees. Out of 53 employees 27 per cent belong to the age group less than 25 years of age, 36 per cent of the employees belong to the age group from 26 to 35 years of age, 30 per cent of the employees belong to the age group from 36 to 45 and the remaining 12 per cent of the employees belong to the age group of above 46 years. The education wise classification of the employees . In that 23 per cent have studied school, 57 per cent have studied graduate, 9 per cent have postgraduate.

TableNo.1Opinionofjobsatisfactionofemployee.

Statement	Mean	Std.Dev
Satisfiedwiththejoboverall	3.7252	0.68753
Satisfiedwiththesalary.	3.2684	0.65563
Workinginthesameorganizationinthenext2 years	4.1018	0.72189
Youthinkyourgrowing inyourcompany	4.8425	0.77658

Managementinterestedinmotivatingtheemployees	2.1423	0.56760
Financialincentivesmotivatearemoreethannon-financialincentives	4.0861	0.63229
Goodphysicalworking conditionareprovided intheorganisation	4.8295	0.65435
Doyousafety atworkshould bethepriority formyorganization	3.2243	0.72403
Doyoufeeltthesmoothrelationshipwiththe employeesmembers equally	4.9198	0.69343
Doyouthink yourmanagertreats allthe employee membersequally	3.7860	0.6450
Managercontinuousfeedbacktohelpachieve	4.8901	0.7104
Satisfiedwiththeappreciationmanagement	4.8622	0.76549

Table no - 2, illustrates the statement of employees satisfaction . Factors were measured withtwelve statements in the five point scale. Further, mean and standard deviation values wererecalculated. From the mean values it is satisfied with the salary (3.26), In the same organizationfornextyear's(4.10),yourgrowinginyourcompany(4.84),Managementmotivatingtheem ployees (2.14), financial incentives (4.08), physical working condition (4.82),safety at workshould be the priority (3.22),you feel the smooth relationship with the employees (3.78),yourmanager treats all the employee members equally (3.78), continuous feedback to help achieve(4.89),satisfied with the appreciation management(4.86).

Table:3.ANOVA–Employeeage

AGEGROUP		N	Mean	Std. Dev	F	Sig.
EmployeeS atisfaction	Lessthan25	11	3.02	0.63	0.486	0.793
	26-35	19	3.01	0.73		
	36–45	16	3.85	0.62		
	46 Above	7	4.91	0.76		

Ho: There is no significant difference between the employees age group

As far as employees satisfaction, the significant value in the ANOVA result indicated at 6 % level of significance with the ‘significant value of 0.793. There is no significant difference in the mean value among their age and behavior. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table:4.ANOVA–Employees Education.

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION		N	Mean	Std. Dev	F	Sig.
Employees Commitment	Schooling	12	2.85	0.57	2.035	0.365
	Graduate	30	3.10	0.66		
	Postgraduate	5	3.09	0.68		
	Profession	6	2.03	0.58		

As far as employee age group is concerned, the significant value in the ANOVA result indicated at 6% level of significance with the ‘significant value of 0.365. There is no significant difference in the mean value among their education and behavior. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

VI. FINDINGS

- Majority of the employees belong to Above 46 years.
- Majority of the employees are male in the company.
- Majority of the employees are graduate.
- Majority of the employees are satisfied with the salary.
- There is no significant difference in the mean value among their age and employees satisfaction. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.
- There is no significant difference in the mean value among their educational qualification and employees commitment. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the study it is found that majority of the employees are satisfied with their jobs. Employees are also satisfied with their salary, structure, promotional programs, working condition, allowance provided by the organization. They are also satisfied with the employer-employee relationship and communication channels in the organization. Majority of the employees are feel secure in this job. Number of employees at accepted that at times there is a considerable flexibility in co-ordinating with work and they are satisfied with the existing interpersonal communication. It was also observed that was there is a scope for the improvement of working condition. Finally I would like to employees are satisfied with their work and organization. ards system provided by the management.

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